

ECO-COMPOSITE MATERIALS FROM NOVEL SOY PROTEIN-BASED BIO-PLASTICS AND NATURAL FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The use of naturally available resources for the manufacture of plastics has gained significant interest in the recent years with growing environmental concerns regarding the disposal of synthetic plastics made from petro-chemicals. Since petroleum resources are limited and an alternative source is sought, biodegradable plastics not only have an ecological advantage over petroleum-based plastics but also have an economical advantage as well. Recent advances in technology proved that the plastics can be made from renewable abundant agricultural resources. Soy protein has been found to be a viable alternative to petro-chemicals in this respect. But so far it has been limited in its use as an adhesive, binder and a packaging material. Research at Michigan State University has been exploring the use of soy protein based biodegradable plastics as structural materials. The processing problems of soy protein are being solved with the use of plasticizers, which can chemically modify it into a polymer resin. A conventional plasticizer used to process soy protein in most of today's research and industrial applications is glycerol. Research is underway to replace the petroleum based glycerol plasticizer with an environmentally friendly plasticizer obtained from renewable resources. In addition to using the plasticizer, soy protein is also blended with a compatible and biodegradable polyester amide to further enhance the mechanical properties and ease the processability. Natural fibers have been added to the above-mentioned blend as reinforcements to produce a biodegradable composite having strength and stiffness suitable for structural applications. The result is a biodegradable, natural fiber-soy protein biocomposite made from renewable resources which can replace glass fiber-synthetic petroleum plastic composites in automotive interior applications and other structural applications.

KEYWORDS: Biodegradable plastics, natural fibers, soy protein, biocomposite, plasticizer, glycerol, hemp, extrusion, mechanical properties, heat deflection temperature.

INTRODUCTION

The components of the biodegradable plastics are derived entirely or almost entirely from renewable raw materials. Recent advances in research and technology have shown that these bio-plastics can be made from abundant agricultural resources. In this respect, soy protein has been considered as a viable alternative to the petroleum polymers in the manufacture of adhesives, plastics, packaging materials and various binders. As early as 5,000 years ago, farmers in China grew soybeans. Soybeans were mechanically crushed for the oil, which was used for lubricants, lamp oil, coatings, cosmetics and waterproofing. In 1804, a Yankee clipper ship brought soybeans to the U.S. In 1829, U.S. farmers first grew soybeans. They raised a variety for soy sauce. During the Civil War, soldiers used soybeans as "coffee berries" to brew "coffee" when real coffee was scarce. In the late 1800s many farmers began to grow soybeans as forage for cattle. In 1904, at the Tuskegee Institute in Tuskegee, AL., George Washington Carver began studying the soybean. His discoveries changed the way people thought about the soybean; no longer was it just a forage crop. Currently valuable products like soy protein and soy oil are extracted from the soy bean.

Figure 1: Year 2002/2003 World Soy bean Production; *Source: Kansas Farm Bureau*

Soybean protein is the major co-product of soybean oil and is readily available, renewable, and has functional properties desired by industry. The soybean crop is the world's foremost provider of protein and oil. Soy protein comprises about 30-45% in mass of the soy bean. Soy proteins are complex macromolecules containing certain amino acid monomers, which determine their properties. The side chains and residuals connected to these monomers significantly affect their physical and chemical

Figure 2: Henry Ford takes an ax to a 1941 Ford automobile to demonstrate the sturdiness of soy-bean based materials. Ford was ahead of his time in testing out natural materials for car parts.

properties. They can readily react with chemicals and incorporate plasticizers during processing. The protein structure can be modified easily to obtain the desired properties. Major protein components include 2S, 7S, 11S and 15S fractions. The 7S fraction makes up to one third of the total soybean proteins and the 11S fraction is approximately half of the soybean proteins.

Natural/Bio-fibers are now emerging as a realistic alternative to glass fibers. Natural fibers have very high specific strength and stiffness that is comparable to that of glass fibers. Advantages of natural fibers over traditional reinforcing fibers such as glass and carbon are: low cost, low density, acceptable specific strength properties, ease of separation, enhanced energy recovery, carbon dioxide sequestration, and biodegradability. Bio-fibers come from renewable resources and are recyclable. Natural fibers also possess excellent sound absorbing efficiency and are more shatter resistant. In addition, natural fibers also offer the possibility to developing countries that natural resources grown within their countries can be used as a material in their composite processing industries. Moreover, reinforcing soy protein plastics using biodegradable and renewable natural fibers will make the final composites completely biodegradable.

This work focuses on developing soy flour based bio-plastic and blending it with a commercial biodegradable polymer and subsequently incorporating natural fibers into it so as to enhance its mechanical properties. Glycerol, which is the most commonly used plasticizer to make the soy protein based plastics, is used to impart flexibility to soy protein by plasticizing it, thus improving its processability. Theories of plasticization are explained from a thermodynamic stand point. The natural fiber used to reinforce the soy bean plastics in the current work is hemp fiber. Hemp is a bast fiber similar to flax, kenaf, jute and ramie and has properties comparable to that of glass fiber.

PLASTICIZATION THERMODYNAMICS

Plasticization introduces pliability and distensibility into a plastic composition. There are two theories, which account for the phenomenon of plasticization, the lubricity and the gel theories. According to the lubricity theory, the plasticizer acts as a lubricant to facilitate movement of resin macromolecules over each other, thus reducing the internal resistance to deformation. The gel theory considers the rigidity in an unplasticized resinous mass to be caused by an internal three-dimensional honey comb structure or gel formed by loose attachments between resin macromolecules which occur at intervals along the molecular chains. The gel theory extends the lubricity theory in that it deals with the idea of the plasticizer acting by breaking the resin – resin attachments and interactions and by masking these centers of attachment from each other, preventing their reformation.

Apart from these theories, the science of thermodynamics, offers two criteria to predict the compatibility of a plasticizer with a base polymer, the Hildebrand solubility parameter, δ , and the Flory interaction parameter, χ . The Hildebrand solubility parameter, δ gives a measure of compatibility between plasticizer and a resin based on the solvating power of the plasticizer for the resin under investigation. The thermodynamic criteria of solubility are based on the free energy of mixing ΔG_M . Two substances are mutually soluble if ΔG_M is negative. By definition,

$$\Delta G_M = \Delta H_M - T\Delta S_M$$

where, ΔH_M = enthalpy of mixing
 ΔS_M = entropy of mixing.

As ΔS_M is generally positive, there is a certain limiting positive value of ΔH_M below which dissolution is possible. According to Hildebrand, the enthalpy of mixing can be calculated by

$$\Delta H_m = \phi_1\phi_2(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2$$

where, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the volume fractions of components 1 and 2 and δ_1 and δ_2 are the solubility parameters of components 1 and 2. From the Hildebrand equation, $\Delta H_m = 0$ if $\delta_1 = \delta_2$, so that the two substances with equal solubility parameters should be mutually miscible soluble due to the negative entropy factor. This is in accordance with the general rule that chemical and structural similarity favors solubility. As the difference between δ_1 and δ_2 increases, the tendency towards miscibility decreases. From the above, it can be concluded that as a requirement for the plasticizer to be effective, the solubility parameters of the resin and the plasticizer must approximately be the same.

	Polar component of Solubility parameter, δ_p	Dispersive component of Solubility parameter, δ_d	Total Solubility parameter, δ_t
Glycerol	17.08	11.83	20.78

Table 1: Solubility parameter of Glycerol

The plasticizer used to plasticize soy protein in the present case is glycerol. Glycerol, a polyol, is a liquid at room temperature and has a melting point of 18°C. Figure 3 represents the molecular structures of Glycerol. The total solubility parameter can be divided into polar and dispersive components, δ_p and δ_d . The total solubility parameter is given as $\delta_t^2 = \delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2$. If the molecular structure of a substance is known,

M.W. = 92

its solubility parameter can be calculated using the method of Hoftyzer and Van Krevlen. This method determines the solubility parameter from the structural group contributions towards the solubility parameter. Using the above mentioned method the values of solubility parameter for glycerol are determined. Table 1 gives the values of solubility parameter of glycerol. Soy flour does not have a definite molecular structure. Hence, the solubility parameter of soy flour cannot be calculated from the theoretical methods. An experimental approach whereby the solubility parameter can be calculated from the surface free energy was used to determine the solubility parameter. The

surface free energy of a substance can be determined by measuring the advancing contact angle with a series of liquids on the surface of the substance under investigation. Pellets of soy flour, 12.75 mm in diameter and 3 mm in thickness were pressed in a Carver press taking care not to contaminate the surface. A Kruss contact angle system was used to determine the contact angles. The system is equipped with a microscope and a video camera, with which it can take the image of the liquid drop of the surface. The system uses different methods for measuring the contact angle of the liquid drop basing on the best fit for the drop on the surface. The following table gives the measure of the contact angles of different liquids on the surface of the soy flour pellet.

Liquid	Contact Angle
Water	70.7
Glycerol	56.9
Ethylene Glycol	39.8
Formamide	32.2
Diiododmethane	59.9

Table 2: Contact Angle Measurements on the surface of Soy flour

Based on the contact angle data, the surface free energy of soy flour was determined. The dispersive component of the surface free energy was found to be 31.3 mJ/m² and the polar component to be 10.3 mJ/m². The total surface free energy was calculated to be 41.4 mJ/m². To determine the solubility parameter from the surface tension, the following empirical relation was used.

$$\gamma = 0.75 E_{\text{coh}}^{2/3}$$

where γ is the surface tension of soy flour and E_{coh} is the cohesive energy density of soy flour. From this relation the cohesive energy density was found to be 410.12 J/cm³. The solubility parameter is given as the square root of the cohesive energy density. The solubility parameter of soy flour calculated experimentally by measuring the surface tension of soy flour was 20.25 (J/cm³)^{1/2}. To confirm the experimental results, soy flour was dissolved in a wide variety of solvents varying in solubility parameters to check for dissolution. It was found the soy flour was miscible only in ethylene glycol and it precipitates leaving a clear solvent in the case of rest of the other solvents. So, it can be said that the solubility parameters of soy flour and ethylene glycol are about the same. The solubility parameter of ethylene glycol was calculated to be 21.12(J/cm³)^{1/2}, and this value matches well with the experimentally determined solubility parameter value of soy flour. Thus the experimentally determined solubility parameter value can be confirmed. On comparing the solubility parameter of soy flour to the solubility parameter of glycerol, it can be found that the values are within +/- 1. This shows that glycerol is compatible and miscible with soy flour and effective in plasticizing it. Thus the use of glycerol as plasticizer in order to process soy flour can be justified thermodynamically. This approach can be used in order to find out novel environmentally friendly renewable resource based plasticizers that are compatible with soy protein.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Soy protein is available in three different forms – soy flour (52% protein), soy concentrate (65% protein) and soy isolate (90% protein). The lower the protein content, the lower is the cost. Soy flour is selected for this work as it is very cost effective and has comparable properties with other forms of soy protein. Archer Daniels Midland (ADM) Company supplied soy flour. Glycerol is used as the plasticizer for mixing with soy flour. The commercial biodegradable plastic that is used to blend with soy flour is a polyester amide. The natural fiber used to fabricate the soy-based bio-composites is industrial grade hemp fiber, which is obtained from Hempline Inc., Canada.

Composition	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Std Dev (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Std Dev (GPa)
A	8.47	0.2	0.22	0.01
A + 15 wt% Hemp	17.81	0.27	1.47	0.11
A + 30 wt% Hemp	19.84	0.44	2.12	0.17

Table 3: Comparison of Tensile Properties of ‘A’ bio-plastic and bio-composites; A: *Soy flour bio-plastic*

Processing: Soy flour, polyester amide and the hemp fiber are all pre-dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C for about 3 hours. Soy flour is pre-mixed with the plasticizer in the weight percentage ratio of 70:30 in a kitchen mixer for 30 minutes. This mixture is fed to a twin-screw extruder ZSK 30 (Werner-Pfleiderer). The extruder has six zones and the temperatures of each of these zones can be controlled. For blending soy flour and glycerol the zone temperatures from 1 – 6 zones were maintained at 95°C, 105°C, 115°C, 125°C, 130°C and 130°C respectively. The extruder was operated at 100 rpm and the torque ranged from 50 – 60% of full scale during processing. The plastic as a result of the blending of soy flour and glycerol is pelletized and mixed with the polyester amide in the weight ratio of 2:1.

Composition	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Std Dev (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Std Dev (GPa)
A	8.32	0.08	0.22	0.01
A + 15 wt% Hemp	26.92	0.56	1.6	0.13
A + 30 wt% Hemp	32.39	1.04	2.5	0.2

Table 4: Comparison of Flexural Properties of soy flour bio-plastic and bio-composites; A: *Soy flour bio-plastic*

This mixture is fed to the extruder with all the zone temperatures at 130°C. The extruder rpm was maintained at 100. The resulting soy flour – polyester amide bio-plastic is pelletized. This soy

Figure 3: Stress-Strain curves of the soy flour bio-plastic and bio-composites; *A: Soy flour bio-plastic*

flour bio-plastic is extruded with 15 and 30-weight percentages of hemp fiber. While extruding the bio-composite, all the zone temperatures on the extruder were maintained at 130°C and the extruder rpm at 100. The final soy flour based bio-composite is pelletized and injection molded. The injection molder used was an 85-ton Cincinnati-Milacron press. The injection molder has four zones and all the zones were maintained between 135°C and 150°C. Materials were injection molded as standard tensile coupons and subsequently used for mechanical and thermal testing.

Analysis and Testing: Injection molded samples were used for Tensile, Flexural and Notched Izod Impact tests complying to ASTM D 638, ASTM D 790 and ASTM D 256 standards respectively.

Composition	Notched Izod Impact Strength (J/m)	Std Dev (J/m)
A	32.91	1.38
A + 15 wt% Hemp	36.72	1.65
A + 30 wt% Hemp	44.72	3.21

Table 5: Comparison of Impact Properties of soy flour bio-plastic and bio-composites; *A: Soy flour bio-plastic*

A United Calibration Corp. SFM – 20 machine was used for tensile and flexural testing. The tensile testing of the bio-plastics and bio-composites was conducted using a load cell of 1000 lbs capacity. A preload of 2 lbs was used. The test speed was 0.2 inches/minute in the case of bio-plastics and 0.05 inches

per minute in the case of bio-composites. The flexural testing of the bio-plastics and bio-composites was conducted using a 20 lbs load cell. A preload of 0.2 lbs was used and the test speed was 0.05 inches/minute in all the cases. The injection molded tensile coupons are cut so that the samples are 2.5"x0.5"x0.125". 0.1" deep notches were cut into the sample beams using a TMI notch cutter. Notched Izod impact testing was performed on a Testing Machines Inc. 43-02-01 Monitor/Impact machine as per the ASTM D256 standard. A 5 ft-lb pendulum was used to impact the samples. Heat Deflection Temperature is determined using a TA instruments 2980 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer. For determining the heat deflection temperature, a constant load of 66 psi is applied at the center of a 3-point bending sample and heated at the rate of 2 degrees per minute from room temperature to 130°C. The sample deflection is recorded as a function of temperature. The tensile and impact fracture surfaces are investigated using Environmental Electron Scanning Spectroscopy referred to as ESEM. The ESEM used for this work is manufactured by Electroscan Corporation (model number – 2020). The imaging pressure (chamber pressure) is set between 2 and 3 Torr. The working distance between the detector and the sample is set between 8 and 10 mm. The accelerating voltage is set at 20 Kv. The sample is focused at different points on its area and micrograph pictures are taken.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composition	Heat Deflection Temperature (deg C)
A	35
A + 15 wt% Hemp	61
A + 30 wt% Hemp	71

Table 6: Heat Deflection Temperatures of the soy flour bio-plastic and soy flour bio-composites; *A: Soy flour bio-plastic*

The soy flour bio-plastics

are used as resin matrix materials for the fabrication of the bio-composites and loaded with hemp fibers. As a general trend, the mechanical properties of all the soy flour bio-plastic-hemp fiber composites increase significantly with the addition of the natural fiber. Table 3 compares the tensile strength and tensile modulus of soy flour bio-plastics and bio-composites. There is an increase of about 135% and 885% in the values of the tensile strength and tensile modulus with the addition of 30-weight percentage of natural fibers. Table 4 compares the flexural properties of soy flour bio-plastics and bio-composites. The flexural strength and flexural modulus improve by about 290% and 1035% respectively with 30-weight percentage fiber loading. Figure 3 gives the Stress vs. Strain curves of the soy flour bio-plastics and bio-composites. With the addition of fiber, there is less elongation before break. Also the bio-composite samples do not yield as much as the bio-plastics before break. The notched Izod impact strength values as shown in table 5 indicate that there is an enhancement in the impact strength as well with the addition of hemp fibers to the soy flour bio-plastic. Heat deflection temperature (HDT) is an important parameter when a material is being used for exterior structural applications. HDT is defined as the temperature at which a material deflects by 0.25 mm under the application of a load (455 KPa or 66 psi). Table 6 gives the values of heat deflection temperatures of the different bio-plastics and the bio-composites. The heat deflection temperature increases significantly by about 35°C with the addition of 30 weight percentage hemp fiber.

Figure 2 is the Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy pictures of the tensile fracture surfaces of the soy flour bio-plastics and bio-composites. It can be seen that in accordance with the Stress vs. Strain plots, the bio-plastic fracture surface has fibrous material extending from the surface, showing good elongation before break. Fiber pullouts are obvious on the bio-composite fracture surface. Bundles of fiber indicate that there is a poor dispersion of the fiber. Also the bare fiber surfaces indicate poor matrix-fiber adhesion.

Soy flour bio-plastic

Soy flour bio-composite

Figure 4: ESEM of Tensile Fracture Surfaces

CONCLUSIONS

Biodegradable composites using a completely biodegradable soy protein based plastic as matrix material and natural fibers as reinforcing materials were fabricated and tested. Soy protein based biodegradable plastics as matrix materials and hemp natural fiber as reinforcing material have been successfully fabricated using the industrial processing techniques of extrusion and injection molding. There is a significant increase in the tensile and flexural properties with the addition of hemp natural fiber to the soy flour bio-plastics. The heat deflection temperature also increased with the increase in fiber content.

Further enhancement in mechanical properties can be obtained by properly dispersing the fiber and enhancing the fiber-matrix adhesion. This can be achieved by employing fiber surface treatments like alkali treatment and silane treatments. Further research is going on to replace the petroleum based glycerol plasticizer with an environmentally friendly plasticizer. Plasticization thermodynamics is being used in order to determine the alternate environmental friendly plasticizer that is compatible with soy protein.

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